

Land Expropriation Bill: Julius Malema's No Compensation Versus African National Congress's Approach to Negotiate

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The debate on land expropriation without compensation has been a central issue in South Africa's socio-political discourse, particularly between the ANC and the EFF under the leadership of Julius Malema. On January 24, 2024, President Cyril Ramaphosa approved a bill allowing land expropriation without compensation, years after the EFF had persistently advocated for its adoption. Notably, while the ANC initially supported the EFF's motion to amend Section 25 of the South African Constitution, the amendment did not secure the required majority vote. However, in subsequent years, the ANC independently pursued and passed the same bill. This raises a critical question: Why did the ANC government, despite having the parliamentary majority, not utilize its power to amend the bill when it was first proposed by the EFF? Had the bill been approved at that time, it would have positioned the EFF as the primary driver of the land expropriation agenda. The key distinction between the two parties lies in their ideological and strategic approaches to land reform. The EFF advocates for a radical and uncompromising stance, arguing that land was historically taken from Black South Africans by force and should therefore be reclaimed by force. In contrast, the ANC adopts a more structured and diplomatic approach, emphasizing expropriation in the public interest to ensure equitable land redistribution, particularly for historically disadvantaged groups. Additionally, the ANC's land reform policy prioritizes redistributing underutilized land to individuals and communities in need, to promote agricultural development, facilitate housing projects, and advancing economic transformation. While both the EFF and the ANC advocate for land expropriation, their policies diverge significantly in terms of implementation. This paper argues that despite their shared rhetoric, the fundamental difference lies in how each party envisions and executes land reform, reflecting broader ideological and strategic distinctions in their political agendas.

Keywords: Land expropriation, economic freedom fighters, African national congress, land reform

Except that the EFF emerged as a breakaway faction from the ANC, their approach to land expropriation differs significantly. The EFF's stance on land expropriation is rooted in a radical vision of decolonizing land ownership in South Africa. The party argues that the enduring inequalities caused by apartheid must be swiftly addressed without compromising a fundamental overhaul of land tenure systems (Xaba, 2020). Central to the EFF's position is the assertion that historical land dispossession, particularly of Black South Africans, justifies land expropriation without compensation. The party contends that addressing land inequities is essential for promoting economic justice, alleviating poverty, ensuring food security, and reducing unemployment. According to Julius Malema, leader of the EFF, a radical policy shift is necessary to achieve

equitable wealth redistribution (Mazwi, 2020). In contrast, while the ANC acknowledges historical injustices related to land dispossession, it advocates for a more diplomatic and incremental approach to land reform. The ANC supports land reform through restitution, redistribution, and tenure reform, emphasizing that expropriation should be conducted within constitutional parameters (Ntsebeza, 2007). Although the party has endorsed land expropriation without compensation, it maintains that this process must adhere to a legal framework that safeguards property rights, fosters investor confidence, and promotes long-term economic stability. The ANC's strategy seeks to balance redressing historical injustices with maintaining economic growth and political stability (Ragolane & Khoza, 2024). Although extensive research has been conducted on South Africa's land reform, there has been limited scholarly focus on the ideological and policy distinctions between these political parties.

Aside from the introduction, this article is structured around three main themes. The first explores the history of land in South Africa, providing essential context for the discussion. The second examines the ANC policy on land expropriation without compensation, which is further divided into two sub-themes: expropriation of land in the public interest and expropriation of unused land. Followed by the EFF radical approach to land reform. Lastly, the paper focuses on the conclusion and recommendations.

History of Land in South Africa

Before analyzing the policy differences between the ANC and the EFF, it is essential to understand the historical context and the factors

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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that led to the formation of these political parties. The contemporary land reform debate in South Africa has been shaped by the legacies of colonialism and apartheid. Prior to these historical periods, land ownership in South Africa was predominantly in the hands of Africans (Maylam, 2017; Mtumane, 2017). Drawing from the work of Maylam (1986) in 1874, approximately five million hectares of land were owned by Black South Africans, who utilized it effectively for both economic stability and welfare before the enactment of the Natives Land Act of 1913. The significance of land ownership among Black South Africans prior to apartheid is highlighted by Bundy (1979) who argues that before the arrival of colonial settlers and the implementation of apartheid policies in 1948, Black South Africans sustained their livelihoods through agricultural activities. Bundy (1979) further notes that during the 19th century, the Nguni nations accumulated land and wealth, particularly following the failure of white-owned farms in KwaZulu-Natal. The inability of white settlers to effectively cultivate the land created an opportunity for Black South Africans to participate in agricultural production and trade. However, this participation was short-lived due to the enactment of exclusionary laws that marginalized Black farmers. Despite these challenges, the Nguni communities remained economically active and engaged in trade (Ehrenreich-Risner, 2022).

One notable aspect of this trade was the concept of "African-grown maize," wherein maize produced in KwaZulu-Natal was transported to Cape Town (Modise & Mtshiselwa, 2013). Despite the restrictive policies of the apartheid regime, Black South Africans continued to play an active role in the economy. Bundy (1979) asserts that during this period, poverty levels among Black communities were relatively low, as most people were able to sustain themselves through farming. The introduction of segregationist legislation further underscored the apartheid government's lack of commitment to fostering economic opportunities for Black South Africans (Rogerson, 2017). Walker (2017) concurs, emphasizing that the National Party government implemented various laws aimed at territorial segregation, which systematically excluded Black South Africans from land ownership.

The Natives Land Act 27 of 1913, particularly Section 1(1), explicitly prohibited Black South Africans from purchasing, leasing, or acquiring land from individuals who were not classified as "natives" without approval from the Governor-General. This legislative framework ensured that Black South Africans were systematically excluded from land ownership and leasing opportunities. Feinberg (2006) highlights that in June 1948, the Union of South African Parliament introduced further restrictions through the Native Land Act, which effectively denied Africans the right to own land in freehold. Subsequently, the apartheid government enacted the Native Trust and Land Act, which established the South African Native Trust, a state agency responsible for overseeing and directing land allocations (Mpya & Ntlama, 2017). This Act eliminated individual land ownership among Black South Africans and introduced a system of trust tenure, managed through the South African Development Trust, a government entity tasked with purchasing land in designated "released areas" for Black settlement (Pheko, 2018).

Kloppers and Pienaar (2014, p. 4) assert that "the Act stripped Black South Africans of their right to own land or even to live outside demarcated areas without proper authorization from the relevant authorities." This legislation further entrenched racial segregation,

ultimately necessitating the post-apartheid land reform initiatives. The challenges associated with land dispossession persisted into the 1950s, marked by a second wave of evictions (Monare, Kotzé, & McKay, 2014). The Group Areas Act of 1950 facilitated the forced removal of Black South Africans from urban areas, designating specific residential and commercial zones for different racial groups. This Act classified the population into four racial categories-White, Native, Indian, and Coloured and restricted Black and Coloured individuals from occupying land designated for White ownership.

Kloppers and Pienaar (2014) further argue that "disqualified persons"-those who did not belong to the designated racial group of a particular area-were prohibited from occupying land or owning immovable property in those regions unless they obtained special permits. The Group Areas Act of 1966 continued to enforce these segregationist policies, consolidating previous legislation and controlling land ownership and occupation (Yengde, 2021). According to Peters (2016), the 1966 Act mirrored the provisions of the 1950 Act, despite introducing a revised classification system that divided the population into three racial categories: White, Bantu, and Coloured. Section 13 of the Act explicitly prohibited the acquisition of immovable property in regulated areas by individuals outside the designated racial group (Mubecua, Mnguni, & Mbatha, 2025).

The cumulative effect of apartheid-era land laws, including the Native Trust and Land Act of 1936, the Group Areas Act of 1950, and the Group Areas Act of 1966, was the systematic exclusion of Black South Africans from land ownership and economic participation (Faboye, 2024). The failure of the pre-democratic government to recognize rural Black communities contributed to high poverty rates and economic marginalization. This raises critical questions regarding how marginalized groups, particularly the poor and women, sustained their livelihoods under these oppressive conditions (Irene, 2017).

In the early 1990s, as South Africa transitioned towards democracy, the apartheid government, under the leadership of F.W. de Klerk, introduced the Abolition of Racially Based Land Measures Act 108 of 1991 (Meyer, 2020). The primary objective of this Act was to repeal previous apartheid land laws that had enforced racial segregation in land ownership and occupation (Mbatha & Mubecua, 2023). The Act came into effect on June 30, 1991 (Iyer & Calvino, 2021) marking a significant step towards dismantling apartheid-era land policies.

According to Graham (2018), the 1994 transition from apartheid to democracy brought about significant political and economic changes in South Africa. The ANC secured a decisive victory in the first democratic elections, winning 62.7% of the vote and obtaining 252 parliamentary seats. This electoral success enabled the ANC to initiate comprehensive land reform policies aimed at addressing the historical injustices of land dispossession and promoting equitable land redistribution.

ANC Policies on Land Expropriation without Compensation

Ever since the ANC gained power in 1994, it has positioned land reform as a critical pillar of economic transformation and social justice in South Africa. The position of the ANC on land expropriation without compensation can be discussed in two-fold, firstly, public interest and expropriation of unused land.

Expropriation of Land for Public Interest

The ANC advocates for land expropriation without compensation in cases where it serves the public interest (Mawere, 2020). Section 25 of the South African Constitution, commonly referred to as the "property clause," allows for land expropriation to promote both economic transformation and social reform, as well as for public purposes (Sibanda, 2019). In 2018, the EFF proposed an amendment to Section 25 of the South African Constitution to enable land expropriation without compensation (Xaba, 2021). This motion was subsequently debated in Parliament, leading to the establishment of the Constitutional Review Committee to assess its feasibility (Cousins, 2022). However, the proposed amendment was ultimately rejected.

The amendment of Section 25 to enable the expropriation of land without compensation, aiming to accelerate land redistribution and promote justice for Black South Africans who were historically dispossessed of their land (Mubecua & Mlambo, 2021).

Land expropriation without compensation in the public interest encompasses various objectives, including land redistribution for housing developments, infrastructure projects, and agricultural reform initiatives (Mubecua & Nojiyeza, 2022). The primary aim is to ensure equitable access to land, particularly for historically disadvantaged groups, such as Black South Africans. State entities, including local government and national departments, have identified large tracts of land that could be expropriated without compensation to address urban housing shortages, support industrial expansion, and enhance food security (Brand South Africa, 2025). According to the ANC, the process of land expropriation without compensation will be conducted in a legal and transparent manner to prevent economic instability (Mubecua & Mlambo, 2020). However, in certain cases, the government may provide compensation, particularly when expropriation involves land with significant commercial investments. The following section focuses specifically on the expropriation of unused land (Erasmus, 2025).

Expropriation of Unused Land

The African National Congress (ANC) has identified vast tracts of unused land and, as a result, has prioritized the expropriation of unutilized and unproductive land as a key policy objective. This initiative primarily targets land owned by absentee landlords, land speculators, and landholders who fail to utilize their farms productively (Matya, 2025). The ANC's land reform policy is particularly focused on redistributing underutilized land to individuals and communities in need, to promote agricultural development, facilitate housing projects, and fostering economic transformation. A key driver of this policy is the need to address rural land shortages and enhance agricultural sustainability, particularly for marginalized and impoverished populations (Nhamo, Mpandeli, Liphadzi, & Mabhaudhi, 2022). According to Manjunatha, Anik, Speelman, and Nuppenau (2013), a significant proportion of arable land remains unused due to inefficient ownership structures and landholding patterns. In this context, land expropriation is viewed as a strategic approach to unlocking economic potential and integrating marginalized rural communities into the formal economy.

The ANC's land reform agenda also underscores the importance of ensuring that beneficiaries of redistributed land receive adequate support, including financial assistance, training, and access to essential resources necessary for productive land use. However,

some scholars (Mfune, 2022; Mfuywa, 2024) argue that the effectiveness of the ANC's land reform policies has been undermined by insufficient post-settlement support, which has led to challenges in sustaining agricultural productivity.

Except that the policy of the ANC intends to push for the expropriation of land without compensation to rectify the injustices of the past and ensure economic transformation, there are many oppositions that the ANC received about the land policy. For example, the investors and commercial farmers (mostly white) have shown concerns about the impact that the land expropriation policy might have on property rights, food security, and economic stability (Kotzé, 2025).

EFF Policies on Land Expropriation Without Compensation

The EFF is widely recognized for its radical stance on land distribution, making it essential to examine the concept of radicalism in the South African political landscape. Historically, Radical Economic Transformation (RET) in South African politics gained prominence in 2015 when it was widely recognized by the media and civil organizations (Desai, 2018). The ANC National Executive Committee (NEC) conceptualized RET as a restructuring of economic ownership and regulatory frameworks to benefit all South Africans, particularly previously disadvantaged groups such as Black South Africans and women (Tleane, 2018).

In January 2017, RET was identified as a crucial mechanism for job creation, economic growth, structural transformation in production, and increased youth participation in economic development (Gumede, 2017). Yingi and Benyera (2024) argue that land reform is one of the key measures necessary to achieve and sustain RET. The slow progress in land restitution and redistribution has been a significant driving force behind the advocacy for RET. The policy sought to transfer land from the white minority to the Black majority. Although the ANC initially proposed a radical approach to land redistribution, it was not fully implemented. In contrast, the EFF has actively championed a more radical land reform strategy, differing significantly from the ANC's more diplomatic and measured approach (Batsani-Ncube, 2021).

The formation of the EFF is closely linked to its leader, Julius Malema, a South African politician who established the party in 2013 following his expulsion from the ANC. Malema had previously served as the President of the ANC Youth League, but his expulsion resulted from controversial statements and disciplinary challenges within the party (Posel, 2013). The EFF quickly gained popularity, particularly among young people and economically marginalized groups in South Africa. Just a year after its founding, the party secured 6.35% of the national vote in the 2014 general elections, earning 25 seats in Parliament. The EFF positioned itself as a vocal opponent of both the ANC and the Democratic Alliance (DA), challenging them on issues such as economic justice, corruption, and governance. Over time, the party has significantly increased its electoral support and expanded its influence within South Africa and beyond (Koekemoer, 2017).

The EFF's political ideology is rooted in radical economic transformation, particularly in land expropriation without compensation. The party advocates for amending Section 25 of the South African Constitution to enable land redistribution without financial restitution to current landowners (Dugard, 2019).

Additionally, the EFF supports the nationalization of private sector enterprises and economic policies that prioritize the needs of the poor (Soldaat, 2024). According to Forde (2014), radicals are generally characterized by profound dissatisfaction with societal conditions and impatience with slow progress. They often advocate for immediate and fundamental transformations, sometimes perceived as revolutionary. A common perception associates radicals with revolutionary ideals and a willingness to instigate societal change, occasionally through confrontational or even violent means. Consequently, responses to radicalism are often severe. However, radical approaches vary considerably. Jankielsohn and Duvenhage (2017) distinguish between two types of radicals: those who adhere to the principle of "I know the good, extend it," which encourages political engagement, and those who follow the notion of "I know the evil, eliminate it," which fosters resistance. Those at the extreme left of the radical spectrum are often labelled "hawks" due to their willingness to employ aggressive methods, whereas those on the right are referred to as "doves," advocating for peaceful protest. In this context, Crowell (2012) argues that Malema has exhibited a radical approach to politics since his tenure as ANC Youth League leader.

The EFF's founding manifesto outlines its approach to land reform, advocating for complete state ownership of all land in South Africa. The manifesto asserts that land transfer should occur without compensation and should apply to all South Africans, regardless of race. The EFF (2014) states, "State custodianship of land will mean that those who currently occupy land should apply for licensing to continue using the land and should clearly state in the application what they want to use the land for over a period of time." Furthermore, under the EFF's proposed land expropriation policy, no individual would have permanent ownership of land (EFF, 2014). Instead, all land leases whether for private corporations or individuals would be limited to a maximum of 30 years, after which renewal would be subject to government approval (Mubecua and Mbatha, 2021). Additionally, the government would reserve the right to expropriate land that is not being utilized effectively (EFF, 2014). This interpretation suggests the complete discontinuation of private land ownership, with the government assuming full control over land administration and regulation.

The radical approach to land reform stems from historical injustices, as land was originally expropriated from Black South Africans without compensation during colonialism and apartheid. Consequently, proponents argue that reversing this process through expropriation without compensation is necessary for economic emancipation. The EFF contends that the lack of land ownership among Black South Africans has perpetuated economic dependency on a system that continues to benefit the white minority (Zindi & Ndhlovu, 2024). As a result, the party has positioned itself as the leading advocate for land ownership reform in South Africa. However, concerns have been raised regarding the perceived retributive nature of this policy. Critics argue that the EFF's approach appears to prioritize redistributing land from white owners to the Black majority rather than fostering comprehensive and sustainable land reform solutions.

Beyond land reform, the EFF has been criticized for rhetoric perceived as fostering hostility toward white South Africans. A particularly controversial example is the song "Kill the Boer, Kill the Farmer," which has elicited strong emotional reactions, particularly among white South Africans (Twala, 2021). While the EFF

dismisses claims that the song incites violence, framing it instead as a historical struggle song, critics argue that it fosters hostility toward white farmers, a demographic that plays a crucial role in South Africa's agricultural sector (Radebe, 2024). Some further assert that such rhetoric contributes to narratives of white genocide, especially given South Africa's high crime rates, including attacks on farmers. Such discourse, they argue, risks exacerbating racial tensions and inciting violence against white farmers (Erasmus, 2019).

Additionally, Jankielsohn and Duvenhage (2017) highlight statements made by Malema that have been interpreted as provocative. For instance, in 2016, Malema stated, "They found peaceful Africans here. They killed them! They slaughtered them, like animals! We are not calling for the slaughter of white people, at least not for now." This statement has been widely regarded as indicative of the party's confrontational stance on racial issues (Grootboom, 2019). Critics argue that rather than addressing the structural injustices of land reform in a manner that promotes reconciliation and sustainable development, the EFF's radical approach often appears as an act of retribution for historical injustices.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this work, the study argues that despite the similarities in the agenda of supporting the land expropriation without compensation, both the ANC and the EFF differ in terms of implementation processes. The policy of the EFF in land policy views the compensation as a strategy that might benefit those who benefited from the land during apartheid and land dispossession. The EFF's radical approach has been criticised for that their policy on land expropriation raises concerns about issues like destroying the confidence of the investors, causing instability in the markets. On the other hand, the ANC believes in a more diplomatic approach to land expropriation, which includes the expropriation of land for public interest. The primary aim is to ensure equitable access to land, particularly for historically disadvantaged groups, such as Black South Africans. State entities, including local government and national departments, have identified large tracts of land that could be expropriated without compensation to address urban housing shortages, support industrial expansion, and enhance food security. Moreover, the ANC's land reform policy is particularly focused on redistributing underutilized land to individuals and communities in need, to promote agricultural development, facilitate housing projects, and fostering economic transformation. A key driver of this policy is the need to address rural land shortages and enhance agricultural sustainability, particularly for marginalized and impoverished populations. The proposed land expropriation approach of the EFF is seen as bold and fast to address the past land injustices, while it might lead to unintended consequences, which include a decline in the investors and affect the productivity of the agriculture. By those who demand a rapid corrective action, the ANC's approach to land might be seen as taking too long, as a result might result in frustration, especially to the poor who lost their land during apartheid and land dispossession.

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Received March 12, 2025

Revision received October 13, 2025

Accepted October 16, 2025